

Colloidal Properties of Alkali and Alkaline Earth Aluminosilicate Hydrosol in Relation to Exchangeable Cations

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The particle size and weight average molecular weight of synthetic colloidal alkali and alkaline earth aluminosilicate hydrosol have been determined by light scattering method. The relation between cation radii and molecular weights of the hydrosol, the extent and mode of aggregation, shape and size of the hydrosol particles have been investigated.

THE synthetic alkali and alkaline earth aluminosilicate hydrosol is a silicate-based system and some of the properties are similar in nature to that of the silicic acid hydrosol. The more active nature of the aluminosilicate hydrosol is related to its structural characteristics¹. In recent years, light scattering method has been applied to a wide variety of high polymeric substances and the results have assisted in understanding the behaviour of long chain molecules. The course of formation of aluminosilicate hydrosol in dilute medium has been studied by light scattering apparatus in relation to molecular growth and the time of gelation². The basis for application of the light scattering method to silicate solutions^{3,4} or in colloidal silicate suspensions⁵ is elucidated by the fundamental investigation of Debye², initially with Nauman³ and then with Anacker⁴. The light scattering technique was found to be extremely sensitive in detecting aggregation in silicic acid in dilute medium⁶. Determination of molecular weights of polymeric silicic acid suspensions were carried out by Greenberg and Sinclair⁷ using a light scattering photometer⁸.

In the present investigation, the shape, size and molecular weight, the important characteristics of the hydrosol upon which colloidal chemical interaction depend, were determined by adopting the technique of light scattering. The above properties were determined as a function of the nature of the exchangeable counterions.

Experimental

Pure and stable alkali aluminosilicate hydrosol, synthesised by the method reported earlier⁹ was converted to different monoionic forms by equilibrium leaching followed by washing and dialysing. T.G.A. experiments were carried out on samples held in a small platinum crucible and suspended by platinum wire from a thermobalance and intro-

duced inside uniform temperature zone of a tubular thermogravimetric furnace. The weight loss was recorded by the thermobalance at suitable time intervals.

Determination of shape, size and molecular weight of hydrosol through light scattering: All the experiments were conducted in a Brice Phoenix 1990-10 universal light scattering photometer series equipped with a spot-light deflection galvanometer. Care was taken to exclude contamination by dust particles and other foreign materials. Double-distilled water was used in the experiments. The required dilutions were made directly in the light scattering cell.

Following Debye's¹⁰ treatment, the shape, size and molecular weight of synthetic colloidal aluminosilicate in very dilute sol were determined. In this treatment, turbidity (τ) is the fractional decrease in the transmitted light intensity, i.e. scattering ratio I_{90}/I_0 . For small randomly distributed monodisperse, isotropic and independent scatterer particles in high dilution, Debye arrived at the equation,

$$\tau = (32\pi^3/3)(\nu^2 n^2/\lambda^4)(1/N)MC$$

where, n is the refractive index of the solvents, $\nu = \delta n/\delta c$ the refractive index increment¹¹, C the concentration (g ml^{-1}), M the molecular weight, and N the Avogadro number. It was demonstrated that the refractive index increment can be considered as a constant if the dilution is sufficiently high. All the values except τ , C and M can then be combined to a new constant H ,

$$\tau/c = HM$$

where, turbidity is proportional to the molecular weights if C is constant or turbidity is proportional to the concentration if the molecular weight (particle size) is the same.

In non-ideal system (colloidal sol), interference between the scattered waves tends to decrease

scattering. This is counterbalanced by the Brownian movement of the colloid molecules producing local homogeneity and as such there is less interference of the scattered waves. Since the Brownian movement is directly related to osmotic pressure, the equation for non-ideal solution can be expressed as

$$\frac{P}{RT} = \frac{C}{M} + BC^2$$

where, P is osmotic pressure, R the gas constant, T the temperature (K), M the molecular weight, C the concentration of the solute, and B is a constant depending on solvent^{1,2}. The following final equation may be arrived at on the basis of the above fundamental consideration,

$$\frac{HC}{\tau} = \frac{1}{M} + 2 BC$$

For determination of shape, the scattering intensities of the hydrosol (0.3%, w/v) were measured at various angles from 40 to 135° in a cell (15 ml) of Witnauer-Scherr type^{1,2} and subsequently the experimental values of $P(\theta)/P(90)$ were calculated corresponding to the values of λ for spheres, which is $2\pi D/\lambda$, and $\sin \theta/2$ (D/λ) was obtained from dissymmetry Z . The dissymmetry was expressed in terms of a ratio of scattering intensities at 45 and 135° using the semi-octagonal dissymmetry cell. The size was calculated from the intrinsic dissymmetry as measured in the semi-octagonal cell for five different concentrations of the hydrosol. The turbidity and dissymmetry were measured in a semi-octagonal cell (45 ml) by noting galvanometer deflection at 0, 45, 90 and 135° at five different concentrations of the hydrosol. The refractive index increment ($\delta n/\delta c$) was determined in a Brice Phoenix differential refractometer calibrated with KCl at 25° and 546 μ wave length and was found to be 0.216.

Molecular weight (weight average) of colloidal aluminosilicate hydrosol : Molecular weight (weight average) was determined in different cationic forms of aluminosilicate hydrosol. The weight average is often the more important average particularly for high polymers, as several physical properties of industrial importance appear to be correlated to it. In the present investigation, the determination of molecular weight of aluminosilicate hydrosol is complicated by the fact that in its polymerisation a range of molecular sizes is obtained. Although for proper characterisation a measure of the distribution of molecular weights should be included, yet in general, most methods provide some average value. Molecular weights were compared with respect to variation of exchangeable cations.

Results and Discussion

The physicochemical characteristics of the prepared hydrosol are represented in Table 1.

Chemical analysis of dried product %	Empirical formula of dried product	Cation-exchange capacity meq/g	Scattering ratio I_{90}/I_0
SiO ₂ = 45.22 Al ₂ O ₃ = 25.68 Na ₂ O = 15.58	Na ₂ O.Al ₂ O ₃ .8SiO ₂ . xH ₂ O	4.5	4.762

The empirical formula (Table 1) indicates the Al₂O₃ : SiO₂ ratio as unity, which is characteristics of substitution of Al^{III} for Si^{IV} ion. The parent sol was sodium aluminosilicate and as such its I_{90}/I_0 value has been mentioned. This I_{90}/I_0 data has been incorporated in the determination of molecular weight (HC/τ) of sols in different cationic forms. I_{90}/I_0 values for each cationic forms are presented in Table 2. The homogeneous nature of the synthesised aluminosilicate hydrogels was established through differential thermogravimetric analysis as each of the prepared hydrogels showed a single peak (Fig. 1) indicating the formation of a single phase hydrosilicate. The above thermogravimetric analysis also confirmed that the synthesised materials were not a mechanical mixture as in the case of formation of mixed hydrosilicates, two or more peaks would have been obtained.

Fig. 1. DTGA peak temperature of aluminosilicate hydrosol in different cationic forms.

The striking feature of the synthetic aluminosilicate hydrosol was significantly the viscosity at lower concentration (indicative of the macromolecular nature) (Table 2), ability to exchange cations in aqueous phase and stability in dilute conditions.

Shape of colloidal aluminosilicate hydrosol molecules : The plots of theoretical values of $P(\theta)/P(90)$ against X (X is related to the characteristics dimension of the molecules) are shown in Fig. 2 by the continuous line and the points show that the theoretical values are very close to that of the experimental values. Thus shape of colloidal dispersed aluminosilicate sol was found to be spherical. The above data was also applied to

Fig. 2. Theoretical values of $P(\theta)/P(90)$ at different X .

other shapes, e.g. rod, random coils and no correlation could be found in case of those shapes due to the deviation observed from the theoretical value. The estimations for rod, random coils were tried but no such correlation was found. Thus shape of the colloidal dispersed aluminosilicate sol was found to be spherical. In the system particles are linked in 'strings of beads' fashion which imparts rigidity to the system. The result is applicable to all the aluminosilicate hydrosol systems studied as the variation was made only in the nature of the exchangeable cations which had no contribution to the intrinsic characteristics of the core structure. The above aspect was proved experimentally with potassium and calcium aluminosilicate hydrosols where similar coincidence of experimental curve was obtained (figures not shown).

Size of colloidal aluminosilicate hydrosol : Intrinsic dissymmetry as determined in a semi-octagonal cell was found to be 4.74 for mechanically shaken sol ; Corresponding $D/\lambda' = 0.475$

$$\text{Hence, } D = \frac{0.475 \times 5460}{1.33} = 1950 \text{ \AA}$$

The above result was obtained for sodium aluminosilicate hydrosol. Similar experiment was conducted for potassium aluminosilicate hydrosol and the value of D was found to be 1785 Å. Thus the result reveals that although the shape did not differ with the variation of exchangeable cation, the size as calculated appeared to follow a direct relationship with the hydrated ionic radius of the cation.

The molecular weights were determined by plotting HC/τ against concentration (C) and extrapolating the curves to zero concentration (Fig. 3). The reciprocals of the intercepts were taken after

Fig. 3. HC/τ values at various concentrations.

making correction for dissymmetry. The results are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—MOLECULAR WEIGHT, SCATTERING RATIO AND VISCOSITY OF ALUMINOSILICATE HYDROSOL IN DIFFERENT CATIONIC FORMS

Cationic form of hydrosol	Molecular weight $\times 10^6$	Scattering ratio I_{90}/I_0	Viscosity of 1% (w/v) sol at 25° cp
Lithium	3.07	3.878	1.17
Sodium	3.77	4.762	1.44
Potassium	4.30	5.432	1.64
Magnesium	5.20	6.568	1.98
Calcium	6.06	7.656	2.31
Barium	6.96	8.792	2.65

From Table 2 it appears that the molecular weight of aluminosilicate hydrosol was very much dependent on particle aggregation which in other ways was solely controlled by the nature of the exchangeable cations. When the alkali and alkaline earth metal series cations were compared separately, the weight average molecular weight was found to be directly related to the cationic radius (Fig. 4). Ionic potential of the individual cation plays an important role in the aggregation of colloidal aluminosilicate particles which has been substantial in the present investigation.

From the nature of the stability of the hydrosol and also the above results it may be concluded that the aluminosilicate system consists of large polymeric molecules and as such the molecular weights of the hydrosol appear to be very important for

Fig. 4. Weight average molecular weights at various cationic radius.

characterisation of associated properties. With the variation of exchangeable cations although the

stability was not significantly impaired, yet the nature of aggregation differed causing variation in the degree of polymerisation. Thus the mode of particle association was related to the dimension and composition of the double layer.

References

1. H. J. WHEATON and F. P. HILDITCH, US Pat. 1 848 127/1932.
2. P. DEBYE, *Ann. Phys.*, 1909, 30, 57.
3. R. V. NAUMAN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1947, 51, 18.
4. E. W. ANACKER, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1951, 55, 645
5. B. N. GHOSH, S. P. MOULIK and S. BANDOPADHYAY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 40, 8.
6. N. K. MITRA and K. L. ROY, *Trans. Indian Ceram. Soc.*, 1972, 31, 52.
7. S. A. GREENBERG and D. SINCLAIR, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, 59, 435.
8. B. A. BRICE, M. HALWER and R. J. SPHISER, *J. Am. Opt. Soc.*, 1950, 40, 768.
9. N. K. MITRA, S. C. DE and S. S. CHATTERJEE, *Trans. Indian Ceram. Soc.*, 1982, 41, 67.
10. P. DEBYE, *J. Phys. Colls. Chem.*, 1947, 51, 18.
11. L. G. LONGWORTH, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 2719.
12. G. OSTER, *Chem. Rev.*, 1948, 43, 319.
13. L. B. WITNAUER and H. J. SCHERR, *Rev. Sci. Instr.*, 1952, 23, 99.